

International Workshop on SMR Safety for a Sustainable Short-term Deployment

Fontenay-aux-Roses, France
17-18 October 2024

Hosted by

INSTITUT DE RADIOPROTECTION ET DE SURETE NUCLEAIRE (IRSN)

31 Avenue de la division Leclerc
92260 Fontenay-aux-Roses,
France

The SASPAM-SA open workshop will promote international exchange of information and practices related to light water SMR safety considering the outcomes both from the current ongoing Horizon Euratom SASPAM-SA project and other EU-projects and Fora (e.g. European SMR Pre-partnership, IAEA, OECD/NEA, ETSON, etc.). The workshop's objective is to share the advancements of the current major research activities on light water SMR safety and give the opportunity to discuss the main results. This allows to identify the needed knowledge development, in the view of additional short-term research actions, and to support the SMR European licensing process.

PROGRAMME

Deadline for Workshop registration: September 15th, 2024

1. SPONSORSHIP

The International Workshop on SMR Safety for a Sustainable Short-term Deployment to be held on 17th – 18th October 2024 in Fontenay-aux-Roses, France, is supported and hosted by the Institut de Radioprotection et de Sûreté Nucléaire (IRSN).

2. BACKGROUND AND OBJECTIVES

Nowadays light water cooled Small Modular Reactor (SMR), are one of the key design options for the near-term deployment of nuclear reactor technology due to their general recognized advantages (inherent safety, design simplicity, possibility of simplified parallel construction, reduction of construction time, and capital and operational cost, etc.) and to their level of technological and licensing readiness.

The technological and licensing readiness of these designs is because light water cooled SMR starts from the well-proven-established operating large-Light Water Reactor technology, incorporate their operational plant experience/feedback, and include moderate evolutionary design modifications acting to increase the inherent safety of the plant. Therefore, it is possible to benefit from the operating large-LWR knowledge and know-how as a base of the SMR technology, minimizing the technological risks connected with innovative technological solutions proposed in advanced/innovative SMRs (that differ significantly from existing operating reactors). Therefore, several light water cooled SMR concepts are in advanced design state and ready to be licensed. Construction and certification activities are currently on-going and are expected to further increase and accelerate.

Considering the Net Zero Goal by 2050 in Europe, nuclear energy will have a key role to reach this target and, at the very beginning of the next decade, light water cooled SMR technology can start to contribute to Europe decarbonization. In the view of the envisaged short-term European countries license process, a R&D program (consistent with the European market needs and license requirements) is in progress to ensure the implementation of the highest nuclear safety standard. Within this regard, the safety demonstration is the key action to confirm the adequacy of the safety provisions ensuring the stable and safe operation of a nuclear power plant in all the plant states. Within this framework, Euratom Research and Training Programs have a key role to support R&D activities, speeding-up licensing process, and secure a leading position for European Intuitions within the international framework. European projects are articulated addressing different topics, in order to support the expected safety demonstration of SMR in Europe, and different actions are in progress or have been recently finished (e.g. ELSMOR, HARMONIZE, MCSAFER, PASTELS, SASPAM-SA, TANDEM).

Considering the outcomes from the current on-going Horizon Euratom SASPAM-SA project (organizer of this event) as well as from the other European projects already finished or currently ongoing and other initiatives in other international FORA (e.g. European SMR Pre-partnership, IAEA, OECD/NEA, ETSO, etc.), the workshop objective is to carry out a comprehensive review to identify remaining knowledge gaps linked to the safety demonstration of light water cooled SMR. The workshop will offer the opportunity to identify the current gaps and how to address them with short-term additional research actions.

3. SCOPE AND TECHNICAL CONTENT OF THE WORKSHOP

The scope considers the safety demonstration of LW-SMRs and the related aspects. Therefore, the focus of the Workshop is to discuss and review the state-of-art and the needed knowledge development on:

- Accident scenarios in LW-SMRs and related phenomenology.
- Capabilities of safety computer codes to predict LW-SMR phenomenology in steady-operational and transient conditions.
- Applicability of existing experimental database to characterize LW-SMR phenomenology in steady-operational and transient conditions.
- Analyses of the current severe accident mitigation strategies and features (e.g. IVMR, hydrogen management, etc) and related modelling aspects.
- Computer code guidelines and best practices for the simulation of LW-SMR.
- Applicability of tools and methods for EPZ in LW-SMR.
- Applicability of high-fidelity tools for the safety analysis of LW-SMRs.
- Safety of LW-SMR integrated into a hybrid energy system.
- Safety research in standardization and nuclear safety.

The workshop consists of seven sessions organized as follows:

SESSION 1: OPENING REMARKS AND INTRODUCTION

SESSION 2: OVERVIEW OF SASPAM-SA PROGRESS

SESSION 3: INTERNATIONAL INITIATIVES

SESSION 4: DISCUSSION OF DAY 1 AND CLOSING REMARKS

SESSION 5: EUROPEAN PROJECT ACHIEVEMENTS

SESSION 6: TECHNICAL PRESENTATIONS

SESSION 7: DISCUSSION AND CLOSING REMARKS

4. PARTICIPATION

The International Workshop on SMR Safety for a Sustainable Short-term Deployment will be open to the public. The number of participants is limited to 70.

5. ORGANIZING COMMITTEE (OC)

The technical content of the workshop has been prepared by the Organizing Committee members:

Ahmed BENTAIB	IRSN	France
Fulvio MASCARI	ENEA	Italy
Fabrizio GABRIELLI	KIT	Germany
Terttaliisa LIND	PSI	Switzerland
Florian FICHOT	IRSN	France
Nils REINKE	GRS	Germany
Mikko ILVONEN	VTT	Finland
Fabio GIANNETTI	UNIROMA1	Italy

6. SCIENTIFIC COMMITTEE (SC)

The technical content of the workshop has been prepared by the Organizing Committee members:

Sanjeev GUPTA	Becker Technologies GmbH	Germany
Claire VAGLIO-GAUDARD	CEA	France
Luis Herranz	CIEMAT	Spain
Andrew MORREALE	CNL	Canada
Mounia BERDAI	CNSC	Canada
Michael MONTOUT	EDF	France
Sylvain TAKENOUTI	EDF	France
Fulvio MASCARI	ENEA	Italy
Ahmed BENTAIB	IRSN	France
Sebastien ISRAEL	IRSN	France
Victor SANCHEZ	KIT	Germany
Egidijus URBONAVICIUS	LEI	Lithuania
Hideo NAKAMURA	JAEA	Japan
Martina ADORNI	OECD/NEA	
Dave LUXAT	SANDIA	USA
Tereza Abrman MARKOVÁ	SUJB	Czech Republic
Shawn CAMPBELL	USNRC	USA
Ville TULKKI	VTT	Finland
Gabriel PAVEL	ENEN	Belgium

7. LANGUAGE OF THE WORKSHOP

The official language of the Seminar will be English.

8. PROCEEDINGS AND SUMMARY REPORT

The proceedings of the workshop will include the presentations and the conclusions summary.

9. CONTACT PERSONS

For technical information, please contact:

Mr. Ahmed Bentaib, IRSN [Tel: +33 1 58 35 98 54, e-mail:ahmed.bentaib@irsn.fr]

For practical information, please contact:

10. MEETING PLACE

The meeting will take place at:

Institut de Radioprotection et de Sûreté Nucléaire (IRSN)
31 Avenue de la division Leclerc
92260 Fontenay-aux-Roses
France

INTERNATIONAL WORKSHOP ON SMR SAFETY FOR A SUSTAINABLE SHORT-TERM DEPLOYMENT

Hosted by Institut de Radioprotection et de Sûreté Nucléaire (IRSN)

Final Agenda

WORKSHOP AGENDA - DAY 1 – 17th October

SESSION 1: OPENING REMARKS AND INTRODUCTION

- 09:00 - 09:10 | Welcome and Introduction - **A. BENTAIB (IRSN), F. MASCARI (ENEA)**
- 09:10 - 09:20 | IRSN Introduction – **P. GIORDANO (IRSN) – Director of Research in Safety**
- 09:20 - 09:30 | Introduction from European Commission - **A. IORIZZO (European Commission)**

SESSION 2: OVERVIEW OF SASPAM-SA PROGRESS

Chair: A. BENTAIB, F. GIANNETTI

- 09:30 - 10:00 | SASPAM-SA overview and current results - **F. MASCARI (ENEA)**
- 10:00 - 10:30 | Analysis of postulated DBA and SA Scenarios in Generic Integral PWR Small Modular Reactor in the frame of the Horizon Euratom SASPAM-SA Projects – **F. GABRIELLI (KIT)**
- 10:30 - 11:00 | Assessment of the relevance and applicability of existing experimental databases to iPWR – **T. LIND (PSI)**

11:00 - 11:50 | Coffee Break + Poster Session

- 11:50 - 12:20 | WP4 Major Insights - **F. FICHOT (IRSN)**
- 12:20 - 12:50 | WP5 Current Activity - **N. REINKE (GRS)**
- 12:50 - 13:20 | Preliminary assessments of EPZ extent in SASPAM-SA WP6 - **M. ILVONEN (VTT)**

13:20 - 14:50 | Lunch and Group photo

SESSION 3: INTERNATIONAL INITIATIVES

Chair: M. ILVONEN, N. REINKE

- 14:50 - 15:15 | CNSC Safety Considerations for the Review of Small Modular Reactors – **M. BERDAI (CNSC)**
- 15:15 - 15:40 | Initiatives in USA - **S. CAMPBELL (USNRC)**
- 15:40 - 16:05 | Accelerating Deployment of SMRs with WGAMA Activities for Reliable Safety Assessment - **H. NAKAMURA (JAEA); M. ADORNI (NEA)**
- 16:05 - 16:30 | Updates on IAEA activities on Emergency Preparedness and Response for Small Modular Reactors- **F. STEPHANI (IAEA)**
- 16:30 - 16:55 | European SMR Pre-Partnership – **S. TAKENOUTI (EDF)**
- 16:55 - 17:20 | Industrial SMR Alliance - **A. AL MAZOUZI (SNETP)**

17:20 - 18:10 | Coffee Break + Poster Session

SESSION 4: DISCUSSION OF DAY 1 AND CLOSING REMARKS

- 18:10 - 18:30 | Discussion and Closing Remarks – **A. BENTAIB (IRSN), F. MASCARI (ENEA)**

WORKSHOP AGENDA - DAY 2 – 18th October

SESSION 5: EUROPEAN PROJECT ACHIEVEMENTS

Chair: T. LIND, F. GABRIELLI

- 09:00 - 09:25 | SEAKNOT: Building a Roadmap on Severe Accidents - **L.E. HERRANZ (CIEMAT)**
- 09:25 - 09:50 | PASTELS: From Experimental to Numerical, Main Results of the Project – **M. MONTOUT (EDF)**
- 09:50 - 10:15 | EASI-SMR project overview - **S. SOBECKI (EDF)**
- 10:15 - 10:40 | ENEN SMR initiative overview - **G. PAVEL (ENEN)**

10:40 - 11:10 | Coffee Break + Poster Session

- 11:10 - 11:35 | AMHYCO Project Overview and First Outcome - **G. JIMENEZ (UPM)**
- 11:35 - 12:00 | McSAFER Project: Main Outcomes and Highlights - **V. SANCHEZ (KIT)**
- 12:00 - 12:25 | The TANDEM Euratom Project to Support the Safe Integration of SMRs into Low-Carbon Hybrid Energy Systems - **C. VAGLIO-GAUDARD (CEA)**
- 12:25 - 12:50 | Review of IAEA Safety Standards in Respect to SMRs Licensing – **E. URBONAVIČIUS (LEI)**
- 12:50 - 13:15 | ASSAS Project: Overview and Key Findings – **L. CHAILAN (IRSN)**

13:15 - 14:45 | Lunch

SESSION 6: TECHNICAL PRESENTATIONS

Chair: F. FICHOT, F. MASCARI

- 14:45 - 15:10 | Validation Database and Future Directions of the THAI Experimental Research for Assessing the Safety of Water-Cooled Small Modular Reactors - **S. GUPTA (BT)**
- 15:10 - 15:35 | Overview of i-SMR design and severe accident analysis using CINEMA code - **J. HAM (KAERI)**
- 15:35 - 16:00 | Advances in MELCOR Modelling Capabilities for Characterizing Small Modular Reactor Safety - **D. LUXAT (SNL)**
- 16:00 - 16:25 | Informing the 4th and 5th Levels of Defence-in-Depth for Water-Cooled SMRs- **L. LEBEL (CNL)**
- 16:25 - 16:50 | Development and Benchmarking of CFD Models of SMR Containment Flow and Aerosol Transport - **S.J. ORMISTON (MANITOBA)**

16:50- 17:10 | Coffee Break + Poster Session

SESSION 7: DISCUSSION AND CLOSING REMARKS

- 17:10 - 18:30 | Discussion and Closing Remarks - **A. BENTAIB (IRSN), F. MASCARI (ENEA)**

POSTER SESSIONS

Name	Title	Institution	Nationality
Laura Gastaldo	The CALIF3S software – a validation case for the safety study of HTGR-hydrogen production coupling systems	IRSN	France
C. Vázquez-Rodríguez, S. Kelm	Development of a LW-SMR dry containment CFD model with containmentFOAM	JULICH	Germany
J. Bittan, M. Di Giuli	EDF and TRACTEBEL contribution in SASPAM-SA	EDF, TRACTEBEL	France
M. Garcia Martin	CIEMAT contribution in SASPAM-SA	CIEMAT	Spain
F. Gabrielli	KIT contribution in SASPAM-SA	KIT	Germany
F. Mascari, F. Giannetti	SASPAM-SA HORIZON EURATOM project	ENEA	Italy
N. Chaumeix	Hydrogen Safety Analysis	CNRS	France
A. Kaliatka	Issues of severe accidents in LW-SMR modelling using AC2 codes	LEI	Lithuania
R. Gencheva	ASTECv3.1.1 sensitivity studies of FPs relies from the DRYWELL to the ENVIRONMENT in IRIS SMR design after LOCA accident and loss of all passive safety systems	INRNE - BAS	Bulgaria
E. Jia	GOTHIC and MELCOR Benchmarking of the CNL Strong Condensation Containment Apparatus Experiments	CNL	Canada
L. Lebel	Simulation of SBO and SBLOCA in a Small BWR Using MELCOR Code	CNL	Canada
L. Lebel	Benchmarking CFD with Gaussian Plume Models for Near-Field Atmospheric Dispersion	CNL	Canada
Y. Okan	Turkey as a SMR Paradise	Nuclear Industry Association of Türkiye	Turkey
T. Sisay Mekonin	Radiation Dose Assessment for CT scanner, Environmental Sample, and their associated lifetime Cancer risk	Wachemo University	Ethiopia
M.S. Shuaibu	Safety Analysis and Risk Assessment of Small Modular Reactors (SMRs) for Next-Generation Nuclear Power	Nigerian Nuclear Regulatory Authority	Nigeria
F. M. Abdulazeez	Safe and Sustainable Energy for Third World Countries: Harnessing the Potential of Small Modular Reactors	Nigerian Nuclear Regulatory Authority	Nigeria

ENEN2+ Mobility POSTERS SESSION

Name	Title	Institution	Nationality
Francesco Rizzo	Methodological Approach to perform Inverse Uncertainty Quantification using RELAP5/Mod3.3 and RAVEN	UNIROMA1	Italy
Abdelfattah Ali	Analysis of Passive Heat Removal Loops for Small Modular Reactors at Supercritical Pressure	Egyptian Atomic Energy Authority	Egypt
Alessandro Morandi	Activation Analysis and Safety Considerations for Compact Tokamak Operations with Deuterium-Helium3 Fuel	Polito	Italy
Cristiano Ciurluini	Development of a 0D Model for the investigation of In Vessel Melt Retention in integral Pressurized Water Reactors	UNIROMA1	Italy
Erik Cilia	Case study of abdba in a generic SMR reactor using MELCOR code	UNIBO	Italy
Fabio Mancini	Sizing of a SMR pressurizer and transient conditions preliminary evaluation	UNIROMA1	Italy
Gianluca D'Arpa	REPAS application for the analysis of the reliability of passive safety systems	UNIPA	Italy
Gianmarco Grippo	DBA Sequence Analysis in a Generic iPWR: Comparison of MELCOR and ASTEC Codes with TRACE Thermal-Hydraulic Reference	UNIBO	Italy
Manuel Venditto	Preliminary fuel Thermal Design of DESIGN 1 LW-SMR	UNIROMA1	Italy
Marcello Principato	DEC-B MELCOR transient analyses in an integral Pressurized Water Reactor	UNIROMA1	Italy
Marcello Savini	Analyses of DBA and severalbdba sequences in a generic iPWR	UNIBO	Italy
Marco Barbieri	OFFBEAT simulation and validation in a Generic iPWR rod under LOCA conditions	UNIBO	Italy
Sara Calistri	Production of radioisotopes of medical interest by 14 MeV neutron beam and radiochemical processes	UNIBO	Italy
Valentina Patitucci	Small modular reactors: a key solution for low-carbon energy transition and enhanced safety through passive systems.	UNIPI	Italy
Federica Vespucci	Application of the beta distribution in probability estimation: comparison between data simulations and REPAS results	UNIPA	Italy
Rainer Kelk	Application of machine-learning methods for condensation in severe accident analysis	PSI	Switzerland